

Solid Waste Management

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Abstract:

It's a basic municipal service provided by municipal authorities in the country to keep cities clean. In India due to industrialization and rural to urban migration population rate is increased. Rapidly growing urbanization problem of solid waste management is occurred in the city. The per capita waste material rate in India has increased from 0.44 kg per day in 2001 to 0.5 kg per day in 2011. Increasing in waste material there is a stress on all infrastructural resources. Vengurla is also one of the well known tourist centre, so need of proper waste collection to save environment from the hazardous waste disposal. This research paper focusing on the process of solid waste management such as storage, collection and disposal of municipal waste in Vengurla.

Key Words: Migration, Urbanization, Solid Waste Management

Introduction:

Solid waste comprises unwanted and discarded materials from houses, roads and from commercial and housing society waste. Use of plastic and other waste causes negative impact on the environment. Improper disposal of solid waste created environmental pollution, disease and other health problem. In Vengurla city primary sources of solid waste are housing society, commercial complex, markets, restaurants, hospitals etc. Waste generated per day is about 50 to 100 metric tons. Vengurla municipal is responsible for storage, collection, transportation and disposal of all solid waste generated in the city.

Significance of the Study:

Before 2015 people living in nearer to dumping ground sell their home, because of they couldn't bear the smell emanating from a 2.6 hectares landfill opposite his place. But after remediation of the landfill many local people come and stay back there and say "feel like we live opposite of a park"

Objective of the Study:

The main objectives of the research paper is to study about the solid waste management system of Vengurla dumping ground and system like day to day collection of waste material

Study Region:

Vengurla is situated in Sindhudurg district

in Maharashtra state. North by Malvan This tahsil, on the south Goa state, East Kudal tahsil and on the west by the Arabian Sea. Its Geographical co-ordinate are 15 52'0" North latitude and longitude is 73 38'0" east. A narrow coastal plain is lies at Vengurla coast. Vengurla has a semi tropical climate and temperature lies between 34 c maximum in summer and 29 c in winter. So temperature is very humid and hot in most of the year. In monsoon there is heavy rainfall approx. 1500 to 2000 mm. The occupational structure of tahsil indicate that fishing and agriculture is the main occupation of people. As per census 2011 has a population of 12,392. The city is governed by a C class municipality, Vengurla municipal council.

Methodology:

1. Field visit: Before monsoon and after monsoon field survey was carried out the Vengurla dumping ground.
2. Primary data: There has been some primary based input through personal interview with questionnaire.
3. Secondary data: This data is collected from news paper, website, periodicals, journal, magazines, books etc. Various article published by scholars and government agencies are used to collect information.
4. Software Techniques: Collected data preserved and brought to the analysis via software like

Arc-Gis, Erdas-Imagine, Arc-View etc.

From 2015 Vengurla municipal collected waste material door to door in 27 categorized. All the waste collected daily in following basis.

Composition of MSW:

Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday	daily
Paper	Plastic	Glass	Puttha	Plastic	Electrical tube	Egg
Rubber tube	Plastic bottles	Bottles		Cloths	Bulb, computers	Tree leafs
Thermocol		Other glass		Chappals	e-west	Coconut, organic waste
		tier		shoes	Mobile	Hair, diaper, sanitary napkin
					Battery cell, TV	Chicken west

Note: Owner is responsible for dead pet animal disposal and building material dispose

Initiatives by the Municipal Council:

1. Announcement of Scheme and capacity building of ULB staff
2. City wide Household Level Sanitation Surveys
3. Awareness Generation and Advertising of Scheme
4. Process of individual toilet construction under SMMU

How Landfill Turns Into Garden:

Vengurla is one of the only cities in India to convert a landfill into a waste management park, which is named as Swatch West Park. This city earns Rs 1.5 lakh per month from processing 7 tons waste generated per day by the town. Under the solid waste management rule, Banned on the usage of plastic bags of less than 50 microns and 500 rupees fine for its usage. Each household was provided with a dustbin to segregate their waste. 25 trained sanitation workers collect waste holding door to door meetings. Dry and wet waste collected differently, 4 vehicles, 1 tractor collect waste every day from the town and transport to dumping ground.

Dumping ground – energy is generated from wet waste through a bio gas plant – from horticulture waste 500 kg responsible for storage, collection, transportation and disposal of all solid waste generated in the city gs of briquette is made per month and sold to local industries – dry waste is recycled – 100 kg of slurry is

produced ,which is used to make compost – low grade plastic is used to build roads – non biodegradable – plastic shredding machine crushes up to 180 kg of light plastic every day – waste plastic used for road building and other plastic sold to cement company

Conclusion:

Before 2015 there was a dirty smell emanating from a 2.6 hectares landfill site, but after remediation of the landfill its turns into a waste management park. This is only one of the towns in India which generates revenue from its waste. Maharashtra government declared “Vasundhara award” 2017 for its green initiatives and successful model for 100 % waste management under the “SWACHH BHARAT ABHIYAAN”. In 2017 at dumping ground 7000 tourist visited in this place. As the country steps up efforts to clean India, Initiatives such as those in Vengurla that is a combination of awareness, innovation can go a long way in transforming WASTE TO WEALTH.

References:

1. Annepu, R.K., 2012. Sustainable solid waste management in India. Department of earth and environmental Engineering. Columbia University, New York
2. Census of India, 2011. Demographic data of Sindhudurg distict.
3. Environmental status report of Vengurla Municipal Corporation
4. Gupta,S.,Mohan.K.,Prasad.R.,1998, Solid waste

- management in India: options and opportunities,
Resources, Conservation and Recycling,
5. Vengurla city sanitation plan,2015, Vengurla
Municipal corporation
 6. International Directory of Solid Waste
Management,1998-1999, The ISWA
 7. Report of the National Commission of
Urbanization,Vol-IV 1988
 8. <http://www.unep.or.jp/ietc/estdir/pub/msw>
 9. <http://edugreen.teri.res.in>
 10. <http://www.mcgm.gov.in>
 11. Municipal Solid Waste Management and
handling, Rule 2000
 12. Maharashtra Plastic carry Bags (manufacture
and usage)rules 2006
 13. State of Environment report- Ministry of
Environment and forest2009